

A digital twin for the Theremin’s Polyphonic Electronic Harmonium from 1967

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present a work-in-progress project focused on creating a functional 3D replica of a unique historical electronic music instrument in virtual reality. The “vacuum tube-based polyphonic electronic harmonium” [1] was constructed in the Laboratory of Acoustics and Sound Recording at the Moscow State Conservatory, presumably in 1967 by the group led by Leon Theremin. Designed for research in melodic and harmonic intonation, the instrument was produced as a single prototype. It was reported to be nonfunctional in the 2000s but was restored in 2024 by a team of researchers from Moscow Tchaikovsky Conservatory Center for Electroacoustic Music (CEAM). This paper outlines the process of creating a life-size virtual replica of the instrument as part of a broader research initiative aimed at preserving multimodal data from unique historical electronic music instruments. Such data primarily includes measurements, sound engines, electronic schematics, visual textures, and interactive kinematic concepts.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Digital twins for cultural preservation

The term “digital twin” refers to a virtual replica of a real-world object or environment, originally developed in engineering [2, 3] and now applied to fields like medicine, archaeology, education, and cultural heritage [4] and more. Its preservational aspect is key for our work.

Electronic music heritage, introduced in university curricula worldwide, includes music instruments. The concept of a tool being an inscription of action is explored in music interface research through terms like “idiomatic playing style” [5], ergographic agent, or “ergogenetic memory” [6], or simply “musical gesture”. To escape contextual specifics of these terms, we talk about “interactive kinematic concept” (IKC), describing the performative kinematics unique to a class of instruments [7]. Digital twins in virtual reality can serve as a good preservation method for instruments and their IKCs, although always secondary to the full restoration of the original machine.

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1.2 Forks empower preservation

The project involves three core components: a 3D model of the object, an interactive sound engine model, and a connection between them. These can be implemented using various techniques, requiring experimental “forks” to find the best configuration. The data, shared between the forks can be as follows.

3D model of the object: The 3D model is key for preservation and should be stored in standard formats (e.g., .obj, .fbx), with textures saved separately.

Sound engine: The sound engine relies on the original instrument’s schematics and/or sound samples, which should be indexed and annotated with interaction descriptions.

Connection between model and sound engine: Recordings of IKCs, such as videos of performers or indexed audio tied to actions, are essential. Rigorous documentation methods, including motion capture and studies of musical gestures [8, 9], can enhance precision.

Multiple forks of a digital twin increase the chances of preserving culturally significant details. For example, while only one physical tube-based polyphonic harmonium from 1967 exists, its digital twin could have numerous forks sharing the same original data.

1.3 VRMIs and procedural audio

Many researchers and developers have contributed to the sphere of Virtual Reality Musical Instruments (VRMIs); see [10, 11] for overviews. Our project is one such application. The engineering root of it is commonly called “procedural audio” - real-time signal processing mapped with dynamic interactions with nonlinear media like virtual reality [12], which can be defined as an immersive simulated 3D environment [13, 14].

The particular procedural audio technique used by us is described in the following.

2. THEREMIN’S POLYPHONIC ELECTRONIC HARMONIUM FROM 1967

Leon Theremin (Lev Sergeevich Termen) constructed several experimental harmoniums (polyphonic instruments) in the late 1920s in New York and during the 1960s in Moscow [15]. In 1992, Keyboard Magazine published a nine-page article about the renowned inventor, co-authored by Robert Moog and Olivia Mattis [16], which included a detailed

interview, combined of two sources: interview by Mattis in 1989 in France and another reportedly conducted by Moog in 1991. There is a brief mention of a polyphonic instrument Theremin had been developing for several years, which appears in different parts of the interviews in Keyboard and in the original by Mattis [17]. In the Keyboard reproduction the response to the question about the “polyphonic instrument” is edited, so when comparing two sources (Keyboard and Mattis) it is not very clear if Theremin was talking about a polyphonic version of his most famous instrument - Theremin (a.k.a. Termenvox), or about some other polyphonic instrument. His most recent recollection of the mysterious machine dates to approximately 1978, when he relocated his workshop from Moscow State University. This account may refer to one of the polyphonic harmoniums constructed in 1960s, although more research needs to be done. Andrey Smirnov, a leading researcher in Soviet music technology and founder of the Theremin Center in Moscow, recalls encountering the specific instrument under investigation during the 1970s at the Acoustics Laboratory of the Moscow State Conservatory (Smirnov, personal communication, January 21, 2025). According to Smirnov, the harmonium remained within the Conservatory building until the 1990s when the Theremin Center took over the space. The last before recent instance of the instrument being powered on and producing sound reportedly occurred during Jean-Michel Jarre’s visit to the Theremin Center in 1997, as part of preparations for his large-scale performance in Moscow [18].

The instrument subsequently continued its quiet existence within the Theremin Center, where one of the authors of this text first encountered it around 2004 or 2005. In 2011, due to the reconstruction of the building and the effective closure of the Theremin Center, the instrument faced the threat of being lost. Reportedly, it was partially damaged by construction workers. A few years later, in 2014, Smirnov moved the instrument to the newly established Moscow Sound Art Studio (a.k.a. SA)_studio), where it remained for several years. It was later transferred to the sound laboratory at Rodchenko’s Art School in Moscow. In 2024, the instrument was transported to the Center of Electroacoustic Music of the Moscow State Conservatory (CEAM), where it underwent comprehensive restoration. The harmonium is now functioning and is permanently exhibited in CEAM’s Artemiev Space.

Leon Theremin likely used the term “harmonium” to describe a class of polyphonic instruments due to their main function - the ability to produce complex harmonies. The only primary source of information about the harmonium under discussion is a 1968 report from the acoustics laboratory, written in Russian, which details several devices designed and constructed by the lab in 1967. The report contains a one-page technical description of the instrument, titled “A precise polyphonic electro-instrument for research on harmonic and melodic intonation” [1], accompanied by two photographs (see Figure 1). The text begins: “Polyphonic electronic harmonium made with radio vacuum tube-based generators...”. Given this description, it is reasonable to refer to the instrument as the “electronic harmonium.” Furthermore, considering that it exists as a single example and was likely part of Theremin’s harmonium series, the designation “Theremin’s electronic harmonium” is also

appropriate. In this text, we will use the abbreviated term “the Harmonium.”

Figure 1. Original photos of the Harmonium from 1968 report, referred to as “image 12” and “image 13”, show the front and back of the machine. Taken from Andrey Smirnov’s archive.

2.1 The Harmonium’s technicality

Essentially, the Harmonium is a collection of 26 modules assembled within a single corpus. Each module comprises a dedicated tube-based tone generator, amplifier, and speaker. The modules are equipped with four controllers. A *key* (located on the front panel), which triggers the sound. A *fine-tune knob* (on the front panel), allowing tuning within a range of ± 50 cents. A *coarse tuning knob* (on the back panel), enabling pitch adjustment over a broader range of approximately two octaves. A *volume knob* (on the back panel), which adjusts the output volume. The total number of keys is 31, though five of these are non-functional due to the absence of circuit contacts beneath them.

One of the primary experimental concepts behind the Harmonium, as described in the report, was the summation of tones in the near acoustic field rather than within the electronic circuit [1]. To achieve this, each generator is paired with its own dedicated speaker.

2.2 Why digitize the Harmonium?

The following points highlight why the Harmonium is an ideal candidate for creating a digital twin to aid in heritage preservation:

It is historical. The Harmonium has a rich developmental history, and is unique, existing as a singular artifact. It was designed with the direct involvement of Leon Theremin.

It works and is available. Thanks to the restoration, we now have a detailed knowledge of many aspects of the instrument.

It is spatially curious. VR allows to engage with three-dimensional aspects of an object. Early electronic instruments are particularly compelling because they lack the spatial standardization imposed by later market-driven demands in music technology. The Harmonium exemplifies this uniqueness.

3. PROOF OF CONCEPT PROTOTYPE

To explore the principal possibility of the realization of the concept described - a simple model has been made in year

2024, using Unity3D game engine (see Figure 2). The interactors were taken from Unity’s XR toolkit [19]. We utilized a LibPD-to-Unity integration for procedural audio processing in real-time [20]. The model is called “LOD>x Keyboard Harmonium” [21] and currently exists as an executable scene for Meta Quest 2 VR set in Unity editor. It allows to approach the front panel of the instrument with use of IKC similar to the original: a key press triggers the generator, and a rotation of a knob allows to tune the pitch (see Figure 3). The sound generator is limited to this two functions and does not have any other similarities to the real Harmonium.

Figure 2. Left: The Harmonium (from video taken by Lydia Kavina in 2024). Center and Right: LOD>x Keyboard Harmonium 3D model built with Unity primitives and example XR UI elements (dials and keys).

Figure 3. A sequence from left to right showing a virtual dial rotation following right hand wrist rotation. This changes the pitch of the specific generator, while the key is pressed (by the left hand) exactly like in a physical Harmonium.

4. MAKING A DIGITAL TWIN

The next stage involves creating a digital twin that inherits a greater degree of data from the original Harmonium. This will be a “LOD=X” prototype, as defined in [21].

4.1 Real-Size 3D Model

A more detailed, real-size model of the Harmonium can be generated using various techniques, including laser-based 3D scanning, automated photogrammetry, or measurement-based modeling. For this developmental fork, we opted for the latter approach. Approximately 100 photographs were captured at CEAM, alongside a comprehensive table of measurements, to construct the model using MAYA 3D software (see Figure 4).

4.2 Sound engine

Building a sound engine for this project can follow two primary paradigms: the first focuses on modeling the electronic circuit, while the second aims to replicate the original sound as closely as possible. In the current iteration of the project we are exploring both paradigms.

Figure 4. Left: One of about 100 photos of The Harmonium at CEAM used for 3D modeling. Right: real-size 3D model in progress.

4.2.1 Wavetable synthesis

One of the ways to replicate the authentic sound of the instrument in an interactive form - is to build a generator, based on a table of original waveforms. As previously described, the Harmonium is conceptually a collection of 26 modules, with each key triggering a dedicated generator. The current fork of the digital twin is at the stage of testing a single module, meaning our work presently focuses on one specific key. A set of 12 distinct samples was recorded using a close-distance microphone positioned near the corresponding speaker (see Figure 5 Left). Each sample was indexed with a detailed description of the IKC, accounting for all controllers associated with the module: the key, the coarse knob, the fine-tune knob, and the volume knob. The resulting dataset comprises more than 12 samples, as some indexed configurations include multiple variations.

Analysis of these recordings revealed the complex behavior of the tube-based generator. For instance, both changes in pitch and volume entail a degree of spectral change, meaning that the generator also works as a filter. At the same time the volume-controlled filtering is more noticeable by ear (see Figure 6).

Figure 5. Left: Recording at the target speaker with a distance of 55 mm. Equipment: microphone Oktava MK-012, Focusrite Clarett interface, Logic pro DAW. All samples are mono, 44100, 32 bit. Right: one period of the waveform, extracted from the recordings.

Figure 6. From left to right: an oscillographic view of the rotation of Volume knob, showing visible “smoothing” of the waveshape.

Our wavetable model utilizes a carefully selected single period from one of the original waveforms (see Figure 5

Right). Principal block diagram shows the structure of the code, made in Pure Data programming environment (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. The schematic view of the wavetable generator in Pure Data (PD). At the top - the controlling parameters, received from the interface. After being scaled - they are mapped to the corresponding parts of the generator. The Volume parameter is seen here controlling additional filter to partly copy the observed behavior of the Harmonium.

4.2.2 Circuit emulation

Modeling electronic circuit of a historical instrument is a difficult task, but it can be approached on different levels of abstraction. Using tools like SPICE (Simulation Program with Integrated Circuit Emphasis) [22] in this case may not be optimal, because of the lack of data about specific components and additional steps on transferring the emulation into a working DSP code. At the same time, it might be possible to analyze circuit and model its general operational processes inside a DSP application.

The complete sound generator circuit diagram was created during the restoration process (see Figure 8). Upon analyzing it, some similarities can be seen with RC oscillators of phase shift type. We can find mentions of similar circuits in the popular radio electronics literature of the mid 20s century - the same period of historical time, from when the Harmonium arrives [23, 24].

In analog oscillators of this type, phase shifts arise from the frequency-dependent impedance of capacitors, which create a feedback network (usually of High-pass filters), working in pair with an inverting active element (in our case a tube). This behavior can be approximated in the discrete-time domain using delays and feedback.

The difference equation (1) exemplifies a simple one-pole filter, based on delay and feedback [25].

$$y(n) = b_0 \cdot x(n) - a_1 \cdot y(n - 1) \quad (1)$$

Here $y(n)$ is the output sample, $x(n)$ is the input one, $y(n - 1)$ is the previous output sample, which is fed back with the coefficient a_1 , which determines the character of the filter (frequency response). The coefficient b_0 allows us to control the maximum gain of the filter [25].

A phase-shift oscillator would generally require a chain of three high-pass (in case of phase-lead behavior) or low-pass (for the phase-log schematics) filters [23, 24, 26]. To

Figure 8. Circuit of the Harmonium's sound generator, made during the restoration in 2024. The interface parts are signed in bold. The active element of the oscillator is a dual-triode 6H9C (a.k.a. 6N9S). Zoom in to see the values.

model a high pass with the equation (1) it is recommended to use positive values of a_1 not higher than 1, and express b_0 as $1 - |a|$, as described in [25].

Equation (1) can be implemented in Pure Data, using the `[fexpr~]` object [27], which allows sample-by-sample operations (see Fig.9).

```
fexpr~ (1 - abs($f2)) * $x1[0] - $f2 * $y1[-1];
```

Figure 9. The same difference equation written in syntax of `[fexpr~]` object in Pure Data.

To model the complete oscillator, we need to combine three of the equations with the addition of an inverted feedback variable. The result is shown in Figure 10. Notice that the frequency coefficient is introduced through additional `[expr]` object in negative, effectively making each filter stage to be a low-pass. This made the digital oscillator more stable in the audible frequency range.

Figure 10. The model of an abstract phase-shift oscillator in PD, made through a series of one-pole filters, acting as an inverting feedback network, exemplifying behavior, similar to the analog oscillator of the Harmonium. Signed are the additional parts of the patch: initial impulse, expected pitch of the note, frequency of the oscillator, adjustment for the feedback gain, and the pitch at the output. The `[v fb]` object is the feedback variable needed to reintroduce it into the first filter equation. It is initiated inside the main object and limited through "min" function. Zoom in to see details.

This current implementation of an abstract model in Pure

Data provides a sinusoidal signal. The precise match between expected and resulting pitches is only possible in certain combinations of frequency and feedback gain. This can probably be improved by making changes in the calculation of the coefficient a_1 . Further work may include an attempt to model the circuit in a less abstract way, with the use of wave digital filters and other techniques [28, 29].

Meanwhile, the working prototype of the LOD=X Harmonium uses the sound engine, based on a Wavetable fork, described earlier.

4.3 Interaction

Similar to the LOD>X prototype mentioned earlier, we are utilizing a LibPD integration with Unity to implement interactive procedural audio processing in this fork. The connection between the virtual controllers and the sound engine is achieved through a collection of custom scripts written in C#. This fork currently exists as an executable scene in Unity editor, compatible with the Meta Quest 3 VR headset via link (see Figure 11).

In this implementation, a user can press a key and fine-tune the pitch on the front panel. To adjust the coarse pitch and volume, the user must move around the virtual instrument (see Figure 12). Volume adjustments are also linked to low-pass filtering; however, the character of the filter does not precisely replicate the behavior of the original samples.

Figure 11. Left and Center: The Harmonium’s digital twin LOD=X prototype front and back. Right: the interactors of the tested module are marked green: a fine-tune knob on the front, a volume-filter knob at the lower back, a coarse knob above it, the corresponding speaker to which the virtual audio source is directed (this mapping models the original).

Figure 12. From left to right: performer first goes to the back and adjusts the volume, then at the front presses the key with one hand and fine-tunes the generator with another.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We presented the conceptual and technical foundation of our ongoing work on creating a digital twin of the tube-based electronic harmonium developed by Leon Theremin’s team around 1967. Similar to the original Harmonium, interacting with its virtual counterpart requires the performer to move around the instrument to adjust pitch and volume, which is a preservation of IKC. The sound engine is a wavetable, using the original waveshape from the real instrument. The 3D model is in real-size and keeps all the original proportions preserved. The level of detail is limited, and we still do not use the original textures.

Future work will focus on developing a sound engine modeled on the instrument’s original electronic circuit (virtual analog), refining the 3D model with authentic textures, exploring different procedural audio techniques, and launching additional developmental forks.

Once completed, the current fork will offer a more immersive and authentic interaction experience. Although never perfect.

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